

**USAGE OF PRINT LIBRARY RESOURCES BY BUSINESS
SUBJECTS STUDENTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS
IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract:

The need to encourage students' constant usage of print library resources for higher academic performance necessitated this study. The study ascertained the usage of print library resources by business subjects' students in secondary schools in Anambra State. One research question guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 3577 business subject students and a sample size of 520 was drawn for the study using stratified random sampling technique. A structured 10-item questionnaire validated by three experts was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was established using test retest method and data analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient yielded reliability coefficients of 0.86. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and z-test to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that business subject students in Anambra State moderately utilize print library resources. It was also found that the business subject students did not differ significantly on their mean responses on the usage of the print library resources based on gender and location of their schools. It was recommended among others that Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC) responsible for the management of secondary schools in Anambra state should jointly fund school libraries with schools authority and Parents Teachers Association (PTA) for adequate provision of print library resources and employment of librarians to assist students, to increase business subject students' usage of library resources for improve academic performance.

Keywords: usage, print library resources, business subjects students

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1. Introduction

Education is universally recognized as an instrument for social, political, scientific and technological development. It is the key factor in the development and advancement of a society. The important function of education is the transfer of instructive knowledge from one generation to the next and the key resource of any nation. Secondary education is the education given to a child between the ages of 11-18 years plus. It is the form of education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary level. The broad aims of secondary education according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) are preparation of students for useful living within the society and for higher education. Specifically, secondary education seeks to provide a higher level of education for all primary school leavers, has a diversified curricular to cater for all and to provide a sub-professional manpower in science, technology and commerce, technical knowledge and vocational skills.

Major areas of skill acquisition in secondary education include business studies, basic technology, practical agriculture, home economics and computer studies (Okoye & Ududo, 2015). At the senior secondary level, each of the integrated subjects is split into many distinct subjects. Business Studies is split into book keeping, financial accounting, commerce, typewriting, office practice, shorthand and keyboarding. Business subjects are intended to enable students acquire practical and vocational skills, attitudes, knowledge and competencies necessary to gain paid employment, self-employment or function effectively in the society (Ogwunte & Okolocha, 2016). Business subjects' curriculum came into being in 2011 academic year with subjects that include office practice, commerce, marketing, insurance, financial accounting and store management.

The curriculum is geared towards wealth creation, entrepreneur development and skill acquisition for self-employment (Oduselu, 2011). In order to implement and achieve these lofty objectives, provisions of different types of educational resources to the students are very important.

Okoli and Aniebue (2018) noted educational resources as inputs in human development that are necessary to achieve objectives in teaching and learning such as human resources, library resources and infrastructure facilities. These resources when effectively utilized in teaching and learning of different school subjects facilitate the achievement of objectives, business subjects inclusive.

Inyang & Enang (2015) posited that School library resources are the raw materials that provide vital services in the teaching and learning process. They contain information in both print and non-print formats such as textbooks, journals, indexes, newspapers and magazines, reports, internet, video tapes, diskettes and microforms. According to Strang (2015), students can access a vast array of resources and use a wide range of books, journals, and other resources that will support and be of benefit to their academic efforts at or through the library. School library resources are important for the preparation of lesson plan by teachers and for educational advancement in order to achieve set instructional objectives.

Print resources are physical items in the library that contain vital information. This refers to information resources available in print format, such as books, periodicals and bound journals (Mawindo, 2005). Print library resources provide overviews, background, history and introduction as well as in-depth examinations of topics. They are useful when an individual is looking for in-depth information on a topic, or background overview of a subject area (Learning Portal, 2016). The use of print library resources by business subject students in secondary schools can appeal to their individual attention by stimulating their interest in making direct personal efforts to perform well.

Usage refers to the way something is used or how much it has been used. Usage as used in this study establishes the fact that print library resources are already being used but determines the degree to which the resources are utilized by the students qualitatively. Utilization of library resources in teaching and learning is being able to employ appropriate instructional material in the library expertly and at the right time in order to attain an instructional objective. This also comprised utilization in teachers and students interaction with the library resources to facilitate learning.

Constant usage of print library resources assists teaching by storing instructional materials such as textbooks, magazines, newspapers, journals and reference materials. It is the function of the library to support the school curriculum by providing up-to-date information to keep teachers and students abreast of new developments (Moruf, 2015). Print library resources promote the development of reading skills and encourage long-term learning habits through reading.

As Mawindo (2005) observed, print library resources especially books provide more in-depth knowledge and broader range of information than that covered in classes. The skill of scanning through books and other publications in the library is critical to discovering useful and relevant materials without wasting precious time on irrelevant documents. Ronald and Frankwell (2014) discovered that the most frequently used library information resources by secondary school students are books and novels. Library information resources as atlas and maps, audio visuals and poetry are not accessible by students

Unfortunately, Moruf (2015) affirmed that school libraries were not effectively utilized by students due to inadequate resources, poor funding and lack of adequate provision for school library development. Other constraints faced by students in the usage of school library include, lack of current and up to date reading materials, restricted reading hours, lack of sitting facilities and lack of informational professional services (Ronald and Frank well, 2014). This consequently, causes poor performance and failures of students in internal and external examinations (Popoola, 2013).

The need for funding for adequate provision of books, machines like photocopiers, librarians for proper library management and assistant to students on use of library facilities cannot be overemphasised. In some cases school libraries fall short of current books for students use and borrow, inadequate and qualified library staff for assisting students with library facilities especially the manner of its use to avoid time waste in looking for materials among others. The library is the powerhouse of the

school resources but of no value to students if they are not adequately utilized. School print library resources should be accessible to students at the right time in their appropriate formats. Olusola (2011) opined that one of the major objectives of any library is to ensure that maximum use is made of its resources and services. No matter how rich a library collection may be, it is believed that if the users do not effectively make use of them, the library collection is regarded as a waste. Accessibility and good usage of print library resources creates enabling environment for increased motivation among students; for active participation in teaching and learning process and improved performance that signifies achievement of course objectives.

The influencing factors on the utilization of print library resources by business subject students in secondary schools could be gender and location. Gender in this study means the physical attributes of a person as a male or female. It is possible that male and female business subject students may differ in their usage of print library resources in secondary schools.

Daramola (2013) stated that male students visit the library more frequently than female students. Daramola also noted that low intensity of library visits among females might be as a result of their perception of the library and the difficulty in combining academic work with home chores. Location in this study means the particular area in the schools where the library is built whether at the centre of the school or outskirts of the school/classrooms.

Ajayi and Ogunyemi (2011) observed that location of the library do influence its usage. Where the library is located at the outskirts of the school premises, students find it difficult to use the resources because the location is not easily accessible and vice versa. However, these assertions are theoretical and need to be empirically proved. Thus, this study to ascertain the usage of print library resources among business subject students in Ogidi education zone of Anambra State.

2. Research Questions

What is the level of usage of print library resources by business subject students in secondary schools in Anambra State?

2.1 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Male and female business subject students do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the usage of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Business subject students do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the usage of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State based on location (center and outskirt).

2.2 Review of Related Literature

Mawindo (2005) noted print library resources as information resources available in print format, namely books, periodicals and bound journals. These Print resources are physical items and provide overviews, background, history and introductions as well as in-depth examinations of topics. (Learning Portal, 2016). Print resources are generally arranged by concept or theory, making their context easier to understand (Fall, 2005). As in the classical conditioning theory propounded by Pavlov (1936), the print library resource provide students with a pleasant environment that stimulates the student's ability to overcome their anxieties and fears of failing exam by making use of the relevant documents. The print library resources will help the student to have access to knowledge, provide them with cognitive tools that allows students to think about their surroundings and resolve problems.

Chidaka (2011) noted that reading materials in libraries are often divided into two basic categories, reference books and circulating books. Circulating books are books that can be checked out and are shelved in the main shelving area of the library. Circulating books cover all subject areas and can range from broad overviews of a general topic to very detailed studies of a very limited, specific topic. They provide more depth information and details on a topic, and include a much broader range of information than that covered in a magazine, journal or newspaper article. Reference books are special types of books, such as encyclopaedias and dictionaries that are referred to for specific pieces of information. Reference books are usually shelved in a special section of the library called the reference section (Chidaka, 2011). Reference books include the following;

- Dictionaries – This is the most familiar and frequently used reference source. There are general and specialized dictionaries just like encyclopedias
- Almanacs & Yearbooks – These are reference books published yearly and contain factual information pertinent to a specific span of time.
- Handbooks & Manuals – This usually normally give a broad treatment of one subject area. Manuals are reference books that explain how something is done or how something operates.

Others are;

- Atlases, which are books filled with maps, charts, and tables. Atlases provide information pertaining to populations and place locations.
- Encyclopedias that provide a general overview of your topic and help to define topics. (Chiadika, 2011).

It is necessary that in developing school library collection, the quality and usefulness of each material should be uppermost in mind, in other to ensure that the materials meet the needs of the targeted users. Teachers also make use of library resources mainly for illustration which makes their teaching easier for students to understand.

3. Method

The study employed descriptive research design. The study was carried out in Ogidi Education zone of Anambra State. The population of this study consisted of all the students offering business subjects' in SSSI to SSSIII in 37 secondary schools in Ogidi Education zone. There are 3577 business subject students from (SSSI 1515, SSSII 1179 and SSSIII 883) in secondary schools in Ogidi zone. A sample of 520 students was used for the study. This was judged to be representative of the total population. The 520 students were selected using the stratified random sampling technique. Data for this study was collected using a 10- item structured questionnaire with 5-point rating scale with response categories and weighted as follows. Very Highly utilized (4.50-5.00), highly utilized (3.50-4.49), Moderately Utilized (2.50- 3.49), Lowly Utilized (1.50-2.49), and Very Lowly Utilized (0.50-1.49). The validity of the instrument was established using the opinions of three experts. The reliability of the instrument was established through test retest method. The data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to obtain the reliability co-efficient of 0.86.

The research instrument was administered to the respondents with the help of three research assistants. Out of the 520 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 497 copies representing 94 percent were duly completed, retrieved and used for data analysis. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and determine the closeness of the respondents' mean ratings respectively. Decisions on the items rated were based on the real limit of numbers and weighted means as indicated.

4. Results

4.1 Research Question: What is the level of usage of print library resources by business subject students in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean ratings on the utilization of print library resources by business subjects students in secondary schools in Anambra State (N= 497)

Print library resources	Mean	SD	Decision
1. I make use of the library catalogue when searching for reading materials	2.17	0.69	Lowly Utilizes
2. I make use of encyclopedias for specific pieces of information	2.26	0.74	Lowly Utilized
3. I go to the library to do my assignment	2.90	0.72	Moderately Utilized
4. I consult the materials in the reference section of the library like magazines or journals	2.77	0.87	Moderately Utilized
5. I read business subjects books in the library for depth and details on a topic	3.38	0.87	Moderately Utilized
6. I make use of library's photocopier to make copies of reading materials	3.18	0.66	Moderately Utilized
7. I make use of dictionaries to find the meaning and origin of	3.21	0.65	Moderately

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words			Utilized
8. I borrow business text books in the reserved section of the library	3.20	0.66	Moderately Utilized
9. I go to the library to read newspapers	1.98	0.66	Lowly Utilized
10. Students use indexes easily for the location of book	1.80	0.69	Lowly Utilized
Cluster Mean	2.67		Moderately Utilized

The item by item analysis in Table 1 shows that out of 10 items rated, four were lowly utilized and six items were moderately utilized. However, the cluster mean of 2.67 revealed that business subject students' usage of print library resource in Anambra State secondary schools was moderate. The standard deviation shows homogeneity amongst responses indicating a greater consensus of opinion.

Hypothesis 1: Male and female business subject students do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the utilization of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: z-test analysis on mean ratings of male and female business subjects students on the utilization of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State

Print library resources	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	P-value	Decision
Male	105	2.67	0.23	495	0.528	Not significant
Female	392	2.69	0.22			

Data in Table 2 show that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business subjects students on the utilization of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is shown by the p-value of 0.528, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected.

Table 3: z-test analysis on mean ratings of business subjects students on the utilization of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State base on location (center and outskirt)

Print library resources	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	P-value	Decision
Centre	163	2.68	0.22	495	0.757	Not significant
Outskirt	334	2.68	0.22			

The data analysis in Table 6 shows that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of business subjects students with library at the centre and those at outskirt on the utilization of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is shown by the p-value of 0.757, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected.

5. Discussion of Findings and Implications of the Study

The findings of the study revealed low utilization of library print resources as encyclopaedias, newspapers, catalogue to search for reading materials and indexes to easily locate books. There is moderate utilization of business subjects' books in the library and their borrowing for depth and detailed study on topics. Others moderately utilized by the business subject students in secondary schools in Anambra State are dictionaries, magazines, journals and photocopiers. However, the cluster mean of 2.67 revealed that business subject students' usage of print library resource in Anambra State secondary schools was moderate. The findings of the study are similar with that of Frankwell (2014) who discovered that the most frequently used library information resources by secondary school students are books and novels. Library information resources as atlas and maps, audio visuals and poetry are not accessible to the students. This means that the students utilize the print materials, mainly business subject books that are related to their class works. As Mawindo (2005) observed, print library resources especially books provide more in-depth knowledge and broader range of information than that covered in classes. The skill of scanning through books and other publications in the library is critical to discovering useful and relevant materials without wasting precious time on irrelevant documents.

However, moderate utilization of the print library resources by the students could be as a result inadequate resources in the library. Moruf (2015) affirmed that school libraries were not effectively utilized by students due to inadequate resources, poor funding and lack of adequate provision for school library development. Other constraints faced by students in the usage of school library include, lack of current and up to date reading materials, restricted reading hours, lack of sitting facilities and lack of informational professional services (Ronald and Frank well, 2014). As Olusola (2011) noted the major objectives of any library is to ensure maximum use of its resources and services. Current materials made available in the library, with enough sitting facilities, reading time and librarians for assistance will increase students' utilization of the print library resources. Utilization of print library resources would motivate student's interest in learning business subjects and facilitate creativity among students thereby leading to higher performance in examinations.

The findings of the study revealed that the business subjects' students did not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the usage of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State based on gender and location. Male and female business subjects students with library at the centre and those at outskirts did not differ significantly in their opinion on the usage of print library resources. This finding is at variance with that of Daramola (2013) that male students visit the library more frequently than female students. This is also against the views of Ajayi and Oguyemi (2011) that location of the library do influence its usage; and that students will find it difficult to use the library resources located at the outskirts of the school premises. This indicates that good knowledge of the importance of library resource usage among

students for good academic performance supersedes any other factor as location or gender issues that could hinder effective use of print library resources.

The findings of this study have implications for Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC) responsible for the management of secondary schools in Anambra state to ensure the provision of adequate print library resource in schools, trainings for business subject teachers and their students for effective usage of print library resource. It also implies that the school management and business subject teachers would educate their students through motivation, on the importance of utilizing the print resources in the school library to improve their academic performance and achieve subject objectives. Adequate librarians should be employed in secondary schools to assist the business subject students on effective usage of the print library resources. The findings also have implications for curriculum planners in vocational education to include effective usage of library resources in the learning experience of the business subject students in secondary schools.

6. Conclusion

Print library resources are necessary ingredients for improved academic performance and the attainment of business subject objectives. The usage of print library resources by business subjects' students in secondary schools in Anambra state is at moderate level. The business subjects' students did not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the usage of print library resources in secondary schools in Anambra State based on gender and location.

6.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations are made:

1. Management of secondary schools in Anambra State should educate business subject students and their teachers on the need for constant usage of print library resources for increased academic performance. This is by collaborating with Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC) through the organization of seminars, workshop to achieve subject objectives.
2. Management of secondary schools should provide enough library study hour on the school time table to enable the students to have a specific time to visit the school library. The inclusion of library study hour on the school time table would afford the students the opportunity to use the library on regular basis.
3. Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC) responsible for the management of secondary schools in Anambra state should jointly fund school libraries with schools management and Parents Teachers Association (PTA). This will make for adequate provision of print library resources and employment of librarians to assist business subject students, to increase their usage of print library resources for improve academic performance.
4. Curriculum planners in vocational education should include usage of library resources in the learning experience of the business subject students in

secondary schools. This is to provide the business subjects students the skills required for effective usage of the library to improve their academic performance.

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